

DEPENDENCE OF THE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE UDDER AND DAIRY PRODUCTS ON THE UDDER SHAPE OF EXPERIMENTAL COWS

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Abstract. *While assessing the degree of adaptation of cow udder to modern milking equipment in livestock herds, it will be of particular importance to assess the morphological and functional characteristics of the Yelin, depending on the dairy productivity of cows.*

Keywords: *cow, udder, milk, cattle, breed, udder circumference, udder length, udder width and diet.*

The aim of the research: to study the effect of milk production by increasing the nutritional value of the feed ration by 10-15% on the main useful characteristics and productivity of imported German Holstein cows in Tashkent region.

Research objectives: to increase the nutritional value of Holstein cows imported from Germany by 10-15% in the first calving period by 10-15% :

to study the level of influence on milk productivity and milk quality indicators when using complete AR diets in the amount of 10-15% of the diet of first-calving cows;

to study the indicators of the cow's exterior, udder, fluffiness, and milk coverage of the feed;

to evaluate some biological characteristics of Holstein cows of German selection;

Research methods. During the research, zootechnical (milk yield, milk quality indicators, exterior, udder, fluffiness, milkiness indicators), biological (clinical, hematological indicators, heat resistance indicator) and statistical (arithmetic means (index and error, variation coefficient), reliability of intergroup differences) were conducted.

Introduction. It is important to suggest that for the increase the milk yield of cows, full feeding is of great importance in increasing the production of dairy products. Because with such feeding, dairy cows are provided with the necessary nutrients, minerals, vitamins and other important elements for the body, which in turn helps to maintain their health, body strength, which is important in increasing resistance to various factors, increasing fertility, and increasing milk yield. Similar opinions can be seen from the conclusions made by many authors based on the results of their research.

At present time increasing the production of meat and milk, the main livestock products assimilated in human evolution, is extremely important for meeting the needs of people on earth for livestock products. The implementation of this factor is carried out primarily by increasing the productivity and quality of livestock products, feeding livestock and improving the breed. In dairy herds, when assessing the level of adaptation of the udder to modern milking equipment, it is important to evaluate the morphological and functional features of the cows' udder. Table 1 shows data on the udder sizes of cows in the experimental group.

Table 1

Udder sizes of cows in the experimental group, sm

Indicators	Groups					
	Control		Experiment I		Experiment II	
	$\bar{X} \pm S\bar{X}$	S _v , %	$\bar{X} \pm S\bar{X}$	S _v , %	$\bar{X} \pm S\bar{X}$	S _v , %
Udder circumference	132,2±1,41	1,06	138,7±1,72**	1,24	135,0±1,27*	0,94
Udder length	44,0±1,0	2,40	48,4±0,95**	1,96	45,8±0,85*	1,86
Udder width	40,0±0,79	2,01	43,7±0,74****	1,70	41,3±0,76	1,86
Udder anterior depth	30,1±0,92	2,58	34,3±0,93**	2,66	30,5±0,87	3,01
Udder posterior depth	33,2±0,88	2,67	38,2±0,99****	2,45	34,0±0,90*	2,57
Fore teat length	8,06±0,47	5,93	8,43±0,77*	9,23	8,24±0,61*	7,50
Hind teat length	7,45±0,48	6,55	8,9±0,65*	8,13	7,92±0,56	7,17
Sucker diameter, mm	2,1±0,39	1,79	2,4±0,30*	1,31	2,5±0,34	1,54
Udder index, %	42,5	-	43,8	-	43,0	-
Udder nominal size, sm ³	3970,0	-	4774,6	-	4134,0	-
Milking speed, kg min	1,27±0,02	2,33	1,36±0,05	4,40	1,30±0,04	3,80

Note: *R<0.05 **R<0.01, ****R<0.001

From Table 1 it can be seen that the udder circumference of cows in experimental groups I and II was 6.5 sm or 4.9% (R<0.01) and 2.8 sm or 2.1% (R<0.05), the udder length was 4.4 sm or 10.0% (R<0.01) and 1.8 sm or 4.1% (R<0.05), udder width was 3.7 sm or 9.2% (R<0.001), udder depth in front was 4.2 sm or 13.9% (R<0.01) and 0.4 sm or 1.3%, udder depth in the back was 5.0 sm or 15.1% (R<0.001) and 0.8 sm or 2.4% (R<0.05), front teat length was 0.37 sm or 4.6% (R<0.05) and 0.18 sm or 2.2% (R<0.05), rear teat length was 1.45 sm or 19.5% (R<0.05) and 0.47 sm or 6.3% (R<0.05), udder index was 1.3 sm and 0.5%, the conventional udder volume was 804.6 or 164.0 sm³, and milk productivity was higher by 7.1 and 2.4%. Also, the diameter of the teats of the cows' udders was within the standard requirements and there was no significant difference between the groups, which indicates their compliance with the requirements of machine milking.

Thus, our studies have shown that the morphofunctional characteristics of the cows' udders and milk yield are significantly dependent on the size of their udders.

Definitely, the content of dry matter, non-fat dry residue of milk and milk sugar in the milk of the experimental cows was at the level of regulatory requirements and indicated the high nutritional value of their milk. The data we provided in the conditions of Uzbekistan in a herd of Holstein cattle indicate that adequate feeding is an important factor determining the nutritional value of milk obtained from cows.

Thus, our studies have shown that the morphofunctional characteristics of the cows' udder and milk yield are in integral dependence on the size of their udder.

Picture 1

Conclusion: By summarizing it should be suggested that the cows of the experimental groups had acceptable technological characteristics of the udder. The udder circumference, length, width, depth of the front and back parts, teat size, udder index of the cows of group II were characterized by higher values than those of the cows of groups I and III, the udder volume was 640.5 and 805.6 sm³, respectively, the milk yield was 3.81 and 6.24%. The udder characteristics of the cows of all groups showed suitability for milking on modern milking equipment.

Practical proposals

1. During the first 90 days of the first lactation in the conditions of Tashkent region, it is proposed to increase the milk yield of cows by 15% when feeding with a 10-15% increase in udder nutrition, udder massage and active feeding.

2. Selection work in a herd of Holstein cows brought from abroad is recommended to be carried out taking into account the optimal age of the first calving, udder shape, period from weaning to calving and live weight determined in studies to increase their milk productivity.

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